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IMAGE CONTOUR SEPARATION ALGORITHMS BASED ON THE THEORY OF FUZZY SETS

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Abstract. In the work, algorithms for isolating the contours of images based on the theory of fuzzy sets are carried out. In this section, the state of the issue of image processing using the concept of fuzzy sets is considered in relation to the following tasks:

Key words: image quality, image segmentation and outlining on images.

Introduction. In applied intelligent image analysis systems, the main functional tasks are image quality assessment, determining the boundaries of an object, classification, clustering and pattern recognition. Distinctive features of the tasks of these types to be solved are: large dimension, the presence of uncertainties in the initial information, the dynamism of changes in the parameters of the external environment, the predictability of which is often difficult or impossible. These features determine the use for solving these problems, along with traditional methods and means of operations research and data mining, intelligent technologies based on informal empirical knowledge of experts and logical reasoning. Examples of such intelligent technologies that have received the greatest development and use are Soft Computing technologies, including fuzzy sets, neural networks, genetic algorithms. One of such ways is the use of soft computing technologies in digital image processing. As you know, these technologies are based on the theory of fuzzy sets, fuzzy logic, neural networks, genetic algorithms, and they are currently used in solving such image processing problems as improving the quality and restoration of images, recognition of objects in the image.

Literature review. Outlining is an important part of many computer vision systems. Ideally, the outlines correspond to the boundaries of the objects, and, therefore, the selection of outlines allows you to segment the image into semantic regions.

However, the concept of “contour” is a rather vague, heuristic, and even subjective concept. In [1-3], the following definition of a contour was given: a contour point is a pixel in the vicinity of which there is a significant local change in intensity; Contours is fragments of an image representing a collection of contour points. As can be seen from this definition, there are several possibilities of fuzzification of the concept of "circuit", because two variables are involved: spatial position and intensity. To date, several fuzzy models are known with the help of which they try to highlight the contours in the image, and some of them are considered in this section. In [3-5], a method for selecting contours is described based on the FIRE (fuzzy inference ruled by else-action-fuzzy conclusion based on ANYWHERE-action) paradigm, which is relatively immune to noise. It uses differences in gray levels in a 3x3 neighborhood as a contribution to fuzzy rules. It was shown in [3-5] that the use of statistical indicators, such as the range and variance of the intensity window, can be as effective as the use of traditional indicators, such as estimating gradients. In [6-10], a method for distinguishing contours based on fuzzy logic is proposed, where local features such as gradient, symmetry, and straightness are combined in order to introduce the concepts of “contour” and “angle”. It states that the traditional definition of a contour point as a point with a high gradient between two uniform flat regions does not work at corners. Despite the successes achieved in the field of digital image processing using the apparatus of fuzzy sets, there are a number of unsolved problems. These include the problem of adequate mapping of the subject area to a fuzzy system, the choice of models of fuzzy inference and their integration into a single intelligent system. Moreover, many of the developed methods based on the theory of fuzzy sets require more computational resources, which complicates their application in applied systems, for example, in biometric access control systems.

Analysis and results. Main idea of the proposed approach is to form a contour image based on the analysis of fuzzy increments for each pixel. In this case, the analysis is carried out by the segmentation method. We represent the image in question as a set of points, consisting of $W \times H$ the proposed algorithm consists of the following steps:

1 Setting the neighborhood of the central element and its increment in a certain direction.

For each central element at this stage, a sliding window of size $W_0 \times H_0$ (usually, $W_0 = 2k_w + 1, H_0 = 2k_H + 1, k_w, k_H$ -natural number. The window data size is set by the parameters k_H at k_w which is determined based on the features of the considered problem of selecting the contours of an object in images. After determining these parameters of the sliding window, a simple increment of the central element in question is calculated (u, v)

$$\Delta(u, v) = J(U + \delta_U U, V + \delta_V V) - J(U, V)$$
$$\delta_U \in \{-k_w, \dots, 0, \dots, k_w\}, \delta_V \in \{-k_H, \dots, 0, \dots, k_H\}, |\delta_U| + |\delta_V| \neq 0, \quad (1)$$

where δ_u, δ_v - integers. In order to simplify the further presentation of the meaning δ_u and δ_v it is assumed that $\delta_u = \delta_v = 1$ Then for each central element (u, v) , eight simple increments can be calculated by the formula (2):

To determine the large (or small) fuzzy increments, we introduce the concepts of the set of fuzzy among the calculated increments. It is known [1-3] that the set of fuzzy increments is determined using the membership function of its elements.

2 Construction of the membership function of a set of fuzzy increments.

At this stage, the membership function of fuzzy increments provide:

- 1) adaptations to noise components when performing fuzzy smoothing;
- 2) the difference between noise and structural objects of the image.

It is known [2, 4] that constructing an membership function in the form of some simple mathematical function is the most convenient, which simplifies the corresponding computational and reduces computational resources. When constructing membership functions, the parametric representation method is used, which provides the prostate of construction. The choice of membership function depends on the problem. In this algorithm, triangular membership functions are used both for input and output. The standard triangular membership function is determined by the formula (2):

$$\mu(x; a, b, c) = \begin{cases} \frac{x-a}{b-a}, & a \leq x \leq b; \\ \frac{c-x}{c-b}, & b \leq x \leq c; \\ 0, & x \geq c. \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

Here: a, b, c -some numerical parameters taking integer values: $a \leq b \leq c$ and $a, b, c, \in \{0, 1, 2, \dots, k\}$ Where, k the number of gradations on the processed image.

Parameters a, c - the base of the triangle, and the parameter b -its top. It should be noted that the reduced membership function generates a normal convex and unimodal fuzzy set with a support - an interval (a, b) , core $\{b\}$ and fashion b . In order to clarify the concept of fuzzy increments, we introduce the qualitative concept of “small”. In the framework of the theory of fuzzy sets. This concept corresponds to fuzzy sets of small numbers can be reduced, i.e. $a=-b, b=0, c=k_0$.

$$\mu_k(x, k_b) = \begin{cases} b, & \text{at } x \in [-k_a, \dots, k_0] \\ 0, & \text{at } x \notin [-k_a, \dots, k_0] \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

Here: $1 - \frac{|x|}{k_a}$ Where k_a -adaptation parameter that characterizes a particular set of small numbers.

The membership functions of qualitative concepts of a large increment can be determined on the basis of formula (3):

$$\mu_k(x) = 1 - \mu_L(x, k_a),$$

After constructing the membership function of the fuzzy increment, it becomes possible to calculate the values of fuzzy increments in all directions.

3 The calculation of the values of fuzzy increments at this stage sets a set of fuzzy rules.

It is known [5–10] that fuzzy rules are constructed from membership functions of the input and input images. These rules define the relationship between the premise and the conclusion, expressed as “if ... then ...”. Phased inputs and outputs greatly simplify the selection of rules and their generalization. Building good rules depends on the amount and quality of knowledge of the image processing expert. However, the description of expert knowledge using the theory of fuzzy sets is not formalized. Therefore, the choice, for example, of the form and parameters of the membership function is arbitrary. When calculating the value of the fuzzy increment for an arbitrary central element in each direction, the corresponding fuzzy rules are used. In cases where the increment is already determined in eight directions, it is set, for example, to calculate the fuzzy increment in the first direction, i.e.

$$d_1(u, v) = J(u - 1, v - 1) - J(u, 0);$$

To calculate fuzzy increment values for a pixel (u, v) the direction of NW, you can use the following rules:

If $(P_1(u, v) = 1)$ then $\Delta_1(u, v)$ tsmall, where $P_1(u, v)$ - predicate describing (characterizing) increments. Calculation of predicate value $P_1(u, v)$ this rule is carried out according to the formula (2):

$$\begin{aligned} P_1(u, v) &= P_1^1(u, v) \vee P_1^2(u, v) \vee P_1^3(u, v), \\ P_1^1(u, v) &= P_1(u, v) \wedge P_1(u - 1, v + 1), \\ P_1^2(u, v) &= P_1(u, v) \wedge P_1(u + 1, v - 1), \\ P_1^3(u, v) &= P_1(u - 1, v + 1) \wedge P_1(u + 1, v - 1), \\ P_1(u, v) &= \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if a } d_1(u, v) \text{ small;} \\ 0, & \text{contrary;} \end{cases} \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

To calculate the increment in all directions, all the rules are used.

$$P_1, P_2, \dots, P_8.$$

4 Determining the contours of images using the segmentation method.

Dividing the image in question into l segments is performed based on the formation of subsets of related pixels. The basic idea of forming subsets of strongly coupled elements is that the elements of each segment will be closer to its “center” than to the “centers” of other segments. The problem of the formation of subsets of strongly coupled elements is considered solved if $\mathfrak{R}$ it was possible to determine the “centers” of segments and the boundaries of the corresponding subsets of elements. Proximity to the central element of segments is determined on the basis of the concept of a fuzzy set [4, 6]. Consider the set of valid elements (i.e., valid pixels) of an image $\mathfrak{R}$. Assume that each valid element P ($P \in R$) matches feature vectors $\bar{\alpha} = (a_1, \dots, a_i, \dots, a_n)$, calculated

in the second stage. The algorithm for fuzzy segmentation of image elements can be described as follows. Let be given parameters l, C_j ($j = 2, l$), which characterize the number of segments and center segments, respectively. Then, to determine the initial partition $R_0(\mathfrak{R}) = \{S_j | S_j \subset \mathfrak{R}\}$, it is possible to calculate the centers of the segments by the formula (1) and the value of the objective function by the formula (2). If for some J ($J \in \{2, \dots, l\}$) and some r_{xy} ($r_{xy} \in \mathfrak{R}$) value

$$\sum_{i=1}^N (r_{xy}^i v_{ij}(x, y)) = 0,$$

then for the corresponding fuzzy segment S_j It is believed that $\mu_j(r_{xy}) = 1$, and for segments S_q ($q = 1, l$), $j \neq q$). It is believed that $\mu_j(r_{xy}) = 0$.

Further, for the obtained fuzzy segments, the refinement of the “centers” of the segments and the value of the objective function, respectively, by the formula (1) and (2). The calculation of the “centers” of the segments is carried out on the basis of an iterative method, which is based on the sequential refinement of the value Z_{ij} (see formula 1) in each iteration. In this case, the value $M_{S_j}(J_u)$ calculated as follows:

$$M_{S_j}(J_u) = \delta_{u_j} / \left(\sum_{v=1}^l \delta r_{u_v} \right),$$

$$\delta_{S_j}(J_u) = 1 / \left(\sum_{i=1}^n r_{i_u} \right),$$

$$J \in \{1, 2, \dots, l\} U \in \{1, 2, \dots, m\}.$$

$$J \in \{1, 2, \dots, l\},$$

During the implementation of the fuzzy segmentation algorithm, the process of refining the “centers” of the segments is carried out. This process is terminated if:

- 1) the condition is satisfied $|\mathcal{D}(\mathcal{R}_{q-1}) - \mathcal{D}(\mathcal{R}_q)| \leq \epsilon$;
- 2) the number of iterations performed q exceeds the specified number q_0 .

Conclusion. To test the operability of the considered algorithm, experimental studies were carried out. The proposed algorithm for extracting the object contours from images was simulated using MATLAB.

The performance of the proposed method is compared with the SOBELI and PREVITT operators. As a result, it was noted that the proposed contouring algorithm is better than the SOBEL and PREVITT operators in finding various edges from images and, thus, can provide a better display of edges, which is impossible in the case of the SOBEL and PREVITT operators.

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